

Self-assembly of simple Schiff base ligand into unique saddle-type [4x4] tetranuclear architecture and its application as selective voltammetric dopamine sensor in aqueous conditions

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ABSTRACT

Dopamine, a crucial catecholamine neurotransmitter, plays essential roles in the operation of the central nervous system in humans. Disrupted dopamine release is associated with neurological disorders and depression, therefore monitoring of dopamine levels is imperative for preliminary disease detection. Development of sensitive and selective sensors for neurotransmitters that function under aqueous conditions is however still challenging, mostly due to the complexity of hybrid nanomaterials that are interacting with the electrode. Here we provide a coordination compound constructed from simple substrates, where subcomponent self-assembly leads to a unique, discrete [4 × 4] saddle-type complex [Cu₄(L-H)₄(BF₄)₂(MeOH)₂](BF₄)₂, which was characterized by ESI-MS and FT-IR techniques, including single crystal X-ray diffraction. The Cu₄L₄ complex was subsequently used for modification of the bare Au electrode based on its accumulation on the electrode surface. The new voltammetric sensor (Au/complex) was applied for dopamine detection alone and in the presence of interfering ascorbic acid by using the Differential Pulse Voltammetry (DPV) techniques under aqueous conditions. In the linear dynamic range (LDR) range from 0.0001 mM to 0.75 mM the dependence of the peak current on dopamine concentration satisfied the following linear regression equation: i_p [mA] = $17 \cdot 10^{-2} c_{DA}$ [mM] + $8 \cdot 10^{-2}$ ($R^2 = 0.998$). Moreover, the excellent limit of dopamine detection (LOD) and the limit of its quantification (LOQ) were established at the level of 5.4 nM and 18.0 nM with accomplished high sensitivity 0.17 A M^{-1} , repeatability as well as reproducibility. Clear separation of the voltammetric signal of dopamine from this one of ascorbic acid, even in the presence of a 100-fold excess of interfering ions found in water, consequently proves that the new prepared sensor can be used as an excellent analytical tool for selective detection of dopamine and ascorbic acid coexisting in the tested samples.

1. Introduction

Dopamine (DA), naturally produced in the human body, is one of the most important neurotransmitters in the central nervous system. It plays a key role in transmitting information between neurons and is responsible for emotional behavior and responses to stimuli. Abnormal levels of dopamine in the body can cause a number of problems, such as Parkinson's, Alzheimer's, Huntington's, schizophrenia and Tourette's syndrome [1–7]. Due to the issues associated with inadequate dopamine levels in the body, it is important to develop a simple and effective method for detecting and determining it. The use of electrochemical methods for this purpose allows for high accuracy, sensitivity and precision. However, detection and selectively determining dopamine in

the body is challenging due to the coexistence of dopamine with other biogenic compounds, such as ascorbic acid (AA) [8–10], which oxidize at bare electrodes within almost the same potential region [4–7]. Therefore, it is necessary to separate the oxidation potentials of these compounds to enable accurate determination of the neurotransmitter. Solving this problem may be facilitated by using modified electrodes as sensors. Among the many ways of modifying electrodes, the use of gold electrodes modified by self-assembled monolayers composed of complex layers for neurotransmitter detection has recently garnered attention in the literature [11–14]. Research has shown that such modification not only facilitates electron exchange between the biomolecule and the electrode surface but also provides effective protection of the metal surface against the adsorption of reaction intermediates and/or end

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products, which can be harmful and even poisonous to the electrode surface and thus affect the qualitative and quantitative efficiency of neurotransmitter detection [15].

Transition metal complex compounds, owing to their ability to accept or deliver electrons, have become a flagship in many fields of research and are among the most widely used compounds in electrochemical processes, including applications in the modification of the gold template for dopamine detection [12]. A very important aspect influencing the utilization of compounds in electrochemistry is their structure, more specifically, the scaffold of organic ligands and the structure of complexes, which is influenced by the coordination preference of the selected transition metal ion [11,16]. Among these, copper complex compounds hold particular significance. Copper ions are frequently employed to coordinate with proteins in multicore complexes, playing a pivotal role in generating active sites of specific proteins, such as dopamine monoxygenase [16–18]. Consequently, electrochemical studies of di-, tri- and tetranuclear transition metal complex compounds, particularly those involving copper, have garnered substantial interest. Additionally, polymetallic compounds are employed due to the presence of metal–oxygen–metal and direct metal–metal linkages, which enhance the redox centers in oxidation/reduction processes [16]. Despite this interest, the existing literature on the utilization of copper complexes for electrode modification in terms of dopamine detection is still now rather scarce. For instance, Jiang et al. described the mercapto-terminated binuclear Cu(II) complex that was applied to modify an Au electrode and revealed an improved selectivity for dopamine detection [16]. In another research group, Boukroune et al. modified an Au/complex electrode using a Cu(II) complex based on a bis-pyrazolyl N-tripodal ligand, which showed high stability and selectivity toward detection of dopamine in the presence of ascorbic and uric acids [19]. These systems however necessitated utilization of the modified thiol groups, which enhance the affinity of the complex to the gold electrode, but render such systems unnecessarily complicated in terms of synthesis, toxicity and overall economy.

Bearing in mind our research group previous experience in the selective detection of neurotransmitters [11,15] and in the synthesis of polymetallic compounds [20–23], in the present study we synthesized a novel tetrametallic complex $[Cu_4(L-H)_4(BF_4)_2(MeOH)_2](BF_4)_2$ based on the *N*-heterocyclic Schiff base ligand (HL) reported previously [24] (Fig.1). Below, in the remainder of the manuscript, the resulting complex will be denoted as Cu_4L_4 .

The composition of the supramolecular architecture allows its adsorption on the gold surface without the need to utilize the thiolic moieties. The newly developed voltammetric sensor (Au/complex) was applied for both standalone dopamine detection and in the presence of interfering ascorbic acid under PBS aqueous conditions, demonstrating excellent selectivity, sensitivity and reproducibility.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Chemicals

Dopaminum hydrochloricum WXF 1 % (specified as 10 mg cm^{-3} , 5 cm^3) solution for infusion was purchased from local chemist's. Other

synthesis reagents: $Cu(CH_3CN)_4BF_4$, MeOH, EtOH, Et_2O and reagents for electrochemical studies: KCl, $Na_2HPO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$, KH_2PO_4 , $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$, NaCl, Na_2SO_4 , KNO_3 , $Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Ca(NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, NaOH, citric acid monohydrate, glycine, dopamine hydrochloride (DA) and L-ascorbic acid (AA) were purchased from commercial sources (Sigma-Aldrich, Fluka and POCh-Gliwice) and used as received without further purification.

2.2. Instrumentation

Infrared spectra were recorded in the range from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} using FT-IR IFS 66/s Bruker spectrometer and ATR-IR Nicolet iS 50. Electrospray ionisation mass spectroscopy (ESI-MS) for methanol solutions in concentration $\sim 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ was performed using Mas ZQ Water spectrometer. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis were carried out by using Quanta 250 FEG, FEI scanning electron microscope with energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDAX). The electrochemical measurements were carried out at room temperature in a three-electrode system with a gold (unmodified or modified) electrode as a working electrode with a geometric area of 0.33 cm^2 , a platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as a reference electrode using the potentiostat/galvanostat analyzer (AUTOLAB PGSTAT 302 N, Eco Chemie, B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands). The pH measurements were performed using pH meter (Model-ULAB 2002).

2.3. Synthesis of ligand HL $[C_{10}H_{11}N_5]$

Ligand HL was prepared in a two-steps synthetic method according to the synthetic protocol reported previously [24] (Scheme S1). The first step was nucleophilic substitution reaction between 2-bromopyridine and an excess of methylhydrazine, and second step, the condensation between obtained primary amine 2-(1-methylhydrazinyl)pyridine with 4-imidazolecarboxaldehyde.

2.4. Synthesis of complex $[Cu_4(L-H)_4(BF_4)_2(MeOH)_2](BF_4)_2$

Cu_4L_4 complex was synthesized in a one pot complexation reaction. Ligand HL (15.0 mg, 0.075 mmol) and $Cu(CH_3CN)_4BF_4$ (23.5 mg, 0.075 mmol) were dissolved in 15 mL methanol. The reaction mixture was magnetically stirred for 24 h at room temperature to give green solution. The reaction mixture was concentrated and added Et_2O . The dark-green precipitate was obtained, filtered *via* suction filtration and washed with Et_2O ($2 \times 5 \text{ ml}$) and dried under vacuum. The crystallization by vial to vial diffusion at low temperature ($4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) of diisopropyl ether to a methanolic solution allowed to obtain crystals proper for X-ray diffraction. Yield: 32.80 mg, 85.3 % based on ligand HL.

ESI-MS (+) *m/z* (%): 264 (100) $[CuL]^+$; ESI-MS (-) *m/z* (%): 1490 (90) $[Cu_4HL_4(BF_4)_5]^-$. IR (KBr cm^{-1}): $\nu(N-H)$ 3440; $\nu(C-H)_{ar}$ 3124, 3067; $\nu(C=N)_{imin}$ 1610; $\nu(C=C)_{ar}$ 1552, 1490; $\nu(C-N)$ 1446, 1322; $\nu(C=N)_{ar}$ 1285, 1224; $\nu(BF_4)$ 1110, 1083; $\gamma(C-H)_{ar}$ 850, 765, 647, 521.

Fig. 1. Self-assembly of ligand HL into its Cu_4L_4 saddle-type complex and application as voltammetric sensor for dopamine neurotransmitter.

2.5. Electrode activation and modification

All solutions under investigated were prepared at room temperature using ultra-pure deionized water and were deaerated with highly pure argon before use. All measurements were conducted in pre-washed laboratory vessels in Piranha solution (persulfuric acid, Caro acid).

Prior to use, the bare gold electrode was polished with aluminum slurries of successively decreasing final grades (down to 0.05 μm , Buehler) on polishing cloths (Buehler). Then, the electrode was electrochemically activated by cycling in the potential range between $E = -0.8$ V and $E = 0.6$ V vs SCE at $dE/dt = 0.1$ Vs^{-1} in 0.5 M sodium hydroxide until the cyclic voltammogram was stable. This procedure avoids structural changes on the gold surface [25]. Then, the activated gold electrode was subjected to modification processes by an accumulation of Cu_4L_4 complex on its surface. In order to do this the activated gold electrode was immersed in phosphate-buffered solution (PBS) (0.06 M; pH 7.0) as the supporting electrolyte solution with addition of 0.01 mM Cu_4L_4 complex and electrochemically cycled in the range of potential from $E = -0.80$ V to $E = 1.15$ V vs SCE at $dE/dt = 0.1$ Vs^{-1} for 10 min with a continuous flow stream of argon over the solution. After obtaining a stable cyclic voltammogram (~ 15 cycles), the electrode was removed from the cell, washed copiously with water, dried in a stream of argon gas and used in further electrochemical measurements. The obtained modified gold electrode has been marked as Au/complex and this designation will be used below in the text. After electrochemical measurements the electrode was washed with water, dried in an argon streaming and was stored in empty tube at room temperature. To confirm the durability of the adsorbed complex layer on the electrode surface, a series of separate experiments were performed in which the modified Au/complex electrode was cycled in PBS, then rinsed copiously with water, immersed in fresh PBS and CVs were recorded (experiment repeated once a day for 5 days). It has been observed that obtained cyclic voltammograms did not alter from the first one CV indicating strong adsorption of the Cu_4L_4 complex on the gold template. To remove accumulated Cu_4L_4 complex from the modified gold surface, the electrode was dipped in a Piranha solution for ~ 5 min and rinsed with water.

2.6. Electrochemical active surface area

The electroactive surface areas of the gold electrode and the Au/complex electrode were evaluated by cyclic voltammetry in 0.1 M KCl with addition of 1 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ as a probe at different scan rates, by

applying the Randles-Ševčík equation: $i_p = 2.69 \cdot 10^5 \cdot A \cdot D^{1/2} \cdot n^{3/2} \cdot v^{1/2} \cdot c$ where i_p [in A] is a peak current, n is a number of electrons involved in the reaction, $A = 0.33$ [in cm^2] is an electrode active surface area, $D = 7.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ [in $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$] is diffusion coefficient of ferricyanides ions in 0.1 M KCl solution, c [in M] is the concentration of $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ and v is the potential scan rate [in $\text{V} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] [26]. According to the scan rate analysis, the peak current obtained on both electrodes were found to be proportional to the square root of the scan rate in the range 0.01–05 $\text{V} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. From the slopes of i_p versus $v^{1/2}$ plots, the electroactive surface area was calculated to be 0.38 cm^2 and 0.495 cm^2 for Au and Au/complex electrode, respectively.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Crystal structure description

The tetracationic complex Cu_4L_4 is C_2 -symmetrical (Fig. 2). Coordination of both Cu^{II} ions can be described as square-pyramidal, with four N atoms from two different deprotonated L ligand molecules as a base; however there are some significant differences. In a case of Cu1, the fifth position (axial) is occupied by F atom of BF_4 anion, and the Cu-F distance is relatively large (2.609 Å; relevant geometric data are listed in Table S1). The CSD analysis shows that such distances are found quite often for $\text{Cu} \cdots \text{F}_4\text{B}$ contacts, while general, for Cu-F bonds the typical distances are much shorter (Fig.S3). For Cu1, four N atoms are almost coplanar (max deviation from the least-squares plane is 0.015(1) Å), the Cu atom is also only slightly displaced 0.055(1) Å, while the F atom is displaced in the same direction by 2.619 Å. For second Cu^{II} ion, Cu2, the fifth coordination place is occupied by water oxygen, and the distance is much shorter; also, the geometry is more distorted: maximum deviation from the four-atoms plane is 0.085(1) Å, Cu is 0.198(1) Å and O(water) – 2.476(2) Å out of the mean plane.

Unlabeled part is related to the label one by symmetry operation $1-x, y, 1/2-z$. $\text{Cu} \cdots \text{F}$ contacts are drawn as thin lines. (b) Channels in the crystal structure of Cu_4L_4 complex (see text).

In the crystal structure there are huge channels (Fig. 2b), filled with the highly disordered solvent molecules; the attempts to model this electron density have not improved the quality of the structure. The voids take as much as 19 % of the volume of the unit cells.

3.2. Electrochemistry of prepared complex on a gold electrode

Cyclic voltammogram of the bare gold electrode recorded in PBS as

Fig. 2. (a) Perspective view of the asymmetric part of the unit cell; the ellipsoids are drawn at the 50 % probability level, hydrogen atoms are represented by spheres of arbitrary radii.

supporting electrolyte in the potential range from $E = -0.8$ V to $E = 1.15$ V vs SCE at $dE/dt = 0.1$ Vs⁻¹ is shown in Fig. 3ab. As can be seen, over a wide potential range ranging from $E = -0.8$ V to $E = 0.6$ V vs SCE, no electrochemical reactions occur. A well-defined anodic peak visible on the CV at 0.93 V vs SCE and cathodic peak at 0.45 V vs SCE are assigned to the gold oxide formation and to its reduction, respectively [27]. In Fig. 3c, an electrochemistry of studied complex (Cu₄L₄) and ligand (HL) is presented. The synthesized ligand is inactive on the gold electrode. Its addition to the supporting electrolyte solution does not alter the cyclic voltammogram. Otherwise, changes in the course of the i - E relationship were noted when the 0.01 mM complex has been added to the solution.

In the potential range of the electrical double layer of gold electrode a well-defined pair of reversible peaks located at 0.25 V and 0.17 V vs SCE is visible. According to the literature this couple of peaks is indicative of electrochemical process of Cu(I)/Cu(II) oxidation and Cu(II)/Cu(I) reduction, respectively [16]. A set of consecutive CVs recorded in the presence of 0.01 mM Cu₄L₄ complex in the potential limits of the electrical double layer is shown on Fig. 3d. It is noteworthy that with increasing number of the successive potential scans (up to 12th cycle) both anodic and cathodic peaks decrease. This indicates formation of an adsorbed layer of complex on the bare gold electrode surface. The conclusion about the Cu₄L₄ complex being adsorbed on the gold electrode surface has been confirmed by the results at various sweep rates (Fig. 4). A linear relationship of the peak current (i_p) versus the scan rate (ν) with high value of the correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9996$) was obtained in the range from 0.02 Vs⁻¹ to 0.50 Vs⁻¹. Moreover, the adsorption of Cu₄L₄ complex at the studied electrode was confirmed by a linear correlation of $\log i_p$ versus $\log \nu$ with a slope of $di_p/d\nu$ close to 1.

3.3. Characterization of the modified electrode

The use of accumulation of Cu₄L₄ complex method for modification of gold electrode brings many benefits, one of the most important of which is to ensure protection of the surface against adsorption of intermediate and/or final reaction products which are harmful and even poisonous for the surface of the bare electrode [15,28]. In order to

obtain accumulated Cu₄L₄ complex on the gold electrode surface it is necessary to choose a suitable system with appropriate features for deposition such as redox transformable, transition metal complexes [12]. Suitable (metallo)supramolecular architectures provide the opportunity to construct artificial compounds that play a key role as a redox center in oxidation/reduction processes. A very important aspect affecting the use of compounds in electrochemistry is their structure, more specifically, the scaffolding of organic ligands and the structure of complexes, which is influenced by the coordination preference of the selected transition metal ion [11,16].

We have chosen copper ion since it is most often used to coordinate with proteins in multicore complexes, which contribute to the generation of active sites of selected proteins, such as dopamine monoxygenase [16]. In addition, the choice of tetrametallic architectures complex is also of great importance because the presence of more metal ions can strengthen the redox centers in oxidation/reduction processes while the application of monometallic systems show difficulties in electrode coating and in the process of chemisorption, which is confirmed in the literature [16,19]. The Cu₄L₄ complex was designed by us to form two active regions, one having affinity for the gold surface and the other providing active sites for dopamine oxidation (Fig. 5).

Moreover, our prediction of the resulting structure was unambiguously confirmed by X-ray characterization and furthermore allow us to determine the nature of Cu₄L₄ complex layer accumulated on the electrode surface. In agreement with our anticipation, one of two areas of the structure involves two methanol molecules coordinated to the metal center and N-heterocycles. In aqueous solution, previously coordinated methanol molecules can be transferred to the solution, as confirmed by ESI-MS analysis. According to the literature, aromatic nitrogen-containing heterocycles can exhibit high affinity for the gold surface [29]. The second area, on the other hand, is a cavity surrounded by four copper ions that constitute an active redox center catalyzing the oxidation of dopamine.

Most importantly, the complex compound we obtained does not contain thiol groups in its structure, which, despite their numerous and well-known disadvantages (susceptible to pH changes, oxidants, organic solvents) [30] are commonly used in modification of gold surface due to

Fig. 3. (a) Cyclic voltammogram of the bare gold electrode in PBS, $dE/dt = 0.1$ Vs⁻¹. (b) the same as in the (a) but in the potential range involved electrical double layer of the gold electrode. (c) The cyclic voltammograms of the bare gold electrode (yellow) in PBS and in the presence of 0.01 mM Cu₄L₄ complex (black) and 0.01 mM ligand (blue), $dE/dt = 0.1$ Vs⁻¹. (d) A set of cyclic voltammograms recorded at the gold electrode during successive cycles in PBS with 0.01 mM Cu₄L₄ complex, $dE/dt = 0.1$ Vs⁻¹.

Fig. 4. The cyclic voltammograms of the Au/complex electrode recorded in PBS at scan rate ranging from 0.02 to 0.50 Vs^{-1} . Insert: the relationships between $i_p - v$ and $\log i_p$ versus $\log v$.

Fig. 5. A representative schematic of the arrangement of the complex during electrochemical measurements highlighting two regions, one associated with the gold electrode surface and the other providing active sites for the oxidation of dopamine.

S-Au bonding. This structural feature makes our system capable of modifying the gold surface and selectively detecting dopamine even more attractive due to, among other things, higher stability. A confirmation on the interaction between the Cu₄L₄ complex and the gold surface is provided by the surface coverage (Γ) calculation by integration of the charge (Q) flowing through the working electrode during the Cu₄L₄ complex electrodeposition from the equation: $Q = n F A \Gamma$ [31] (where: n - the number of electrons involved in the electron transfer process; F - the Faraday's constant; A - geometric area of the electrode). The surface coverage was estimated to be about 10.8 $nmol\ cm^{-2}$. The obtained Γ value allowed estimating the area per adsorbed molecule of

the Cu₄L₄ which was 0.17 nm^2 and it is in agreement with the above findings. Moreover, it should be underlined that the calculated values of the surface coverage and the area per one adsorbed molecule of the Cu₄L₄ are compatible with the observed increase in the active surface area obtained by the modifying the gold electrode which demonstrates an improvement in the electroactivity of the electrode surface after modification in comparison with active surface area before modification. It is worth adding that adsorption of the Cu₄L₄ complex not only effectively protects the electrode surface from adsorption of poisonous reaction products, but also increases the electrode surface area and facilitates target transfer of electrons between the oxidized compound and

the gold electrode.

The surface morphology and chemical composition of both the bare gold electrode and the modified Au/complex electrode were investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDAX), which confirmed the modification of the bare gold electrode with Cu_4L_4 complex (Fig. 6). It can be clearly seen that the modification of the bare gold template with Cu_4L_4 complex drastically affects its morphology. The surface of the unmodified Au electrode is characterized by uniform surface material (Fig. 6a). Meanwhile the SEM image of the modified Au/complex electrode shows the process of accumulation of the complex on its surface, resulting in a relatively wide size distribution (Fig. 6b) and the formation of an irregular system with a tendency to aggregation. According to previously published [11], nitrogen-functionalized organic compounds form well-organized and compact monolayers on Au electrode. Most likely, such a structure provides easier access for possible reactants to the electrode surface. In addition, the EDAX analysis nicely showed the homogeneous distribution of elements in the tested sample, which is another proof of confirming that the adsorption of the used complex on the gold electrode surface has taken place (Fig. 6c–h). The latter is additionally proved by X-ray energy dispersion spectrum (see, Figs. S5, S6). Next, gold electrode surface modification by Cu_4L_4 complex has been confirmed by Attenuated Total Reflectance Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-IR) spectra, where the $\text{C}=\text{N}/\text{C}-\text{N}$ bands shifts observed in $1500\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions (Fig. S7) are evidence of the high affinity of aromatic nitrogen-containing heterocycles to the gold template. The adsorbed

layer of the Cu_4L_4 complex on the surface of the electrode can effectively protect poisoning of the modified electrode surface by intermediate and/or final products of the redox processes under study.

3.4. Electrochemical behavior of dopamine at modified electrode

The modified Au/complex electrode has been used to study the electrochemical behavior of dopamine. The difference between the cyclic voltammograms recorded at the bare and at the Au/complex electrode in the presence of 0.5 mM dopamine is depicted at Fig. 7.

As can be seen, electrooxidation/electroreduction processes of dopamine at Au as well as at Au/complex electrode occur in two potential ranges as evidenced by the presence of 2 pairs of quasi-reversible peaks on the CVs. This is in accordance with the commonly known mechanism [32] presented below (Fig. 8).

At the bare gold electrode, according to the above scheme, an oxidation peak at $E = 0.32\text{ V}$ is responsible to quasi-reversible oxidation of dopamine to o-dopaminoquinone which in the reverse scan undergoes reduction at $E = 0.17\text{ V}$. The peak-to-peak separation (ΔE_p) for these processes is equal to 150 mV. The change of the bare Au electrode to the Au/complex modified one shifts potentials of the two above aforementioned processes toward lower values and so oxidation/reduction process occur at $E = 0.23\text{ V}$ and at $E = 0.13\text{ V}$, respectively. In the case of the Au/complex electrode, ΔE_p for processed occurred in the first step of the above adopted mechanism is approximately 100 mV. The second stage of the mechanism includes transformation of dopaminequinone to

Fig. 6. SEM images of (a) the bare gold surface and (b) modified Au/complex electrode. (c–h) EDAX analysis of Au/complex electrode.

Fig. 7. Second scans of CVs recorded at the bare gold electrode (yellow) in PBS and in the presence of 0.5 mM DA (green), second scans of CVs recorded at the Au/complex electrode in PBS (black) and in the presence of 0.5 mM DA (red), $dE/dt = 0.1 \text{ Vs}^{-1}$.

leucodopaminochrome and it is not associated with electron exchange, it is chemical in nature. The subsequent couple of peaks at $E = -0.08 \text{ V}$ and at $E = -0.20 \text{ V}$ ($\Delta E_p = 120 \text{ mV}$) visible on the CV obtained for Au electrode is associated with quasi-reversible process of dopaminochrome formation. The location of these peaks shifts when the process occurs on the electrode modified by Cu_4L_4 and the pair of peaks under consideration appears at $E = -0.12 \text{ V}$ and at $E = -0.30 \text{ V}$ ($\Delta E_p = 180 \text{ mV}$). For clarity of the picture for Au + DA and Au/complex + DA systems, the second scans are shown in Fig. 7. This kind of presentation makes it easier to show both above described electrochemical steps. It should be noted that in addition to the potential shift of the observed redox processes, the replacement of the bare gold electrode with the modified one also results in an increase in the intensity of current signals. The latter together with the shift of the considered redox processes towards lower potentials, undoubtedly testifies to the catalytic effect of the Cu_4L_4 complex being accumulated at the electrode surface on the considered processes of dopamine. Note that the potential range at which the peak pair associated with the electrooxidation/electroreduction of dopamine to o-dopaminoquinone visible on CV overlaps with potential range of the oxidation/reduction of the Cu_4L_4 complex

(Fig. 7), while at the same time the current response of dopamine at the Au/complex modified electrode is about 7.5 times higher. This observation strongly proves that the voltammetric response of dopamine is catalytically mediated by the Cu_4L_4 complex modified gold template.

3.5. Effect on pH on the electrocatalytic activity of dopamine at modified electrode

To examine the effect of pH on the position and intensity of oxidation signal of DA pH of the supporting electrolyte solution was varied from 3 to 11. An observation in Fig. 9 reveals a strong pH dependence of current signal with a maximum in the range of 6–8. Thus, supporting electrolyte solution at pH 7.0 close to physiological pH in human fluids was chosen for subsequent investigations. As it could be expected peak potential moves linearly toward less positive values with pH increasing and in the pH range from 3 to 11 the following equation is fulfilled: $E_p = -0.060 \text{ pH} + 0.64$, ($R^2 = 0.9996$). The value of $dE_p/d\text{pH}$ slope equal 0.06 indicates that during oxidation of DA on the Au/complex electrode the number of electrons exchanged is equal to the number of protons released [33].

3.6. Effect on scan rate on the electrocatalytic activity of dopamine at modified electrode

The dependence of the potential scan rate on the redox process provides some important kinetic information. A set of cycle voltammograms recorded on the Au/complex electrode with different scan rates is shown in Fig. 10a. As established, a linear relationship between the peak current and the square root of scan rate was obtained in the range from 0.02 Vs^{-1} to 0.50 Vs^{-1} , Fig. 10b. Analysis of the experimental data generated the following linear regression equation: $i_p [\text{mA}] = 0.45 v^{1/2} + 0.02$ ($R^2 = 0.993$). This result proves that under the experimental conditions used, the overall rate of DA oxidation is limited by diffusion being slower than both adsorption of DA and following charge transfer at the electrode/solution interface. This conclusion is additionally supported by the value of $d \log i/d \log v$ slope being very close to 0.5 [26]. It should be stressed that a diffusion-controlled electrode process is favorable for quantitative determination of analyte concentration in electrolyte solution.

Fig. 8. Mechanism of dopamine electrooxidation.

Fig. 9. (a) CVs of Au/complex electrode in supporting electrolyte with various pH in the presence of 0.05 mM DA, $dE/dt = 0.1 \text{ Vs}^{-1}$. (b) effect of pH on the peak current (blue) and the peak potential (red) during DA electrooxidation.

Fig. 10. (a) The CVs recorded at the modified gold electrode containing 0.5 mM of dopamine in PBS at various scan rates (0.02 and 0.50 Vs^{-1}). (b) the relationship between $i_p - v^{1/2}$ for the oxidation signal.

3.7. Electrochemical determination of dopamine

In the next stage of the study, the analytical sensitivity of the Au/complex electrode was determined for the quantification of dopamine by differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) in the DA concentration range from 0.0001 to 1.5 mM. The corresponding DPV voltammograms are presented in Fig. 11a (for the picture clarity only some DPV curves for selected DA concentrations are shown).

As follows from the course of DPVs, with increasing dopamine content in the bulk of solution the anodic peak current increases (for each tested concentration measurements were triplicated). The relationship between the peak current and the DA concentration is presented in Fig. 11b. According to Fig. 11b, the peak current increased linearly from 0.0001 mM to 0.75 mM of dopamine. In this linear dynamic range (LDR), as established by using the at least square method, the following linear regression equation is satisfied: i_p [mA] = $17 \cdot 10^{-2} c_{\text{DA}}$ [mM] + $8 \cdot 10^{-2}$ ($R^2 = 0.9989$). At the DA concentration higher than 0.875 mM, the oxidation current started to diminish, which may be evidence that above this concentration DA begins to adsorb on the modified electrode surface [34]. At the same time the detection sensitivity (i_p/c_{DA}) at $dE/dt = 0.1 \text{ Vs}^{-1}$ was determined to be equal to 0.17 A M^{-1} . Moreover, the limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ) estimated according to formulas: $\text{LOD} = 3 S_b / S$ and $\text{LOQ} = 10 S_b / S$, where: S_b is the standard deviation of current in the supporting electrolyte solution evaluated on the basis of 10 times repeated DPV measurements, S is the slope of the linear i vs c_{analyte} dependence [35], were established at the level of 5.4 nM and 18.0 nM, respectively. The values of electroanalytical parameters obtained for the prepared electrochemical sensor based on the Au/complex conductive material are collected in Table 1 and are compared with these ones evaluated for other sensors published in the

Table 1

Representative results of the DA sensing at various modified electrodes.

Type of electrode	Range of linearity [μM]	LOD [nM]	Sensitivity	Ref.
Au electrode modified by binuclear Cu(II) complex	0.2–30	80	–	[16]
Au electrode modified by Mn(II) complex	0.0001–850	6.8	$4.11 \text{ A M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	[11]
Graphite electrode modified by Cu(II) complex	–	500	$2.01 \text{ A M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	[36]
MWCNT/[Cu(sal-ala)bpy] nanocomposite modified GCE	0.1–300	160	$2.3455 \text{ A M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	[37]
PGE modified by Cu/Cu ₂ O nanoparticles	0.3–53	1060	0.51 A M^{-1}	[38]
Dopamine polymer film	1–600	200	–	[34]
CPE/ $\text{K}_2[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL}^{\text{NNN}})_2]$	0.25–100	12	0.180 A M^{-1}	[12]
GR-SWCNT-Ce-Cu-Tween 20/GCE	0.1–100	7.2	–	[6]
GPE modified by PDI-CuO	5–500	6	$4 \text{ A M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	[39]
GPE modified by La@CuO-DMT	10–1500	21	$13.9 \text{ A M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	[40]
GPE modified by Cu-Ag bimetallic	0.1–200	26	$1.56 \text{ A M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	[41]
Au electrode modified by tetranuclear Cu(II)	0.1–750	5.4	0.17 A M^{-1}	This work

literature. This comparison gives rise to the conclusion that the Au/complex is a promising platform for the electrochemical determination of DA in real samples.

Fig. 11. (a) The DPVs recorded at the Au/complex electrode in addition of various concentration of dopamine in PBS, $dE/dt = 0.1 \text{ Vs}^{-1}$. Insert: The excerpts of DPVs recorded for the lowest concentrations (red dashed line). (b) the relationship $i_p - c_{\text{DA}}$ in the dopamine concentration range (0.0001–1.5 mM). Insert: $i_p - c_{\text{DA}}$ in the narrow dopamine concentration range (0.0001 to 0.1 mM). Error bars correspond to the standard deviations of the measurements ($n = 3$).

The practical application of the developed Au/complex sensor was tested by DPV voltammetry for determination of DA in a commercially available DA solution for infusion. For this purpose, the calibration method was used [42]. To do so the content of the ampoule with this solution (specified as 10 mg cm^{-3} , 5 cm^3) was diluted and spiked with known amount of DA standard solution. For each tested solution the measurements were triplicated. The calibration curve was used to determine the concentration of each solution. The results are summarized in Table 2 together with the recovery and RSD. As can be seen, the concentrations found are very close to their nominal content in each sample. The recovery values varied from 98.9 % to 100.7 % confirm that the developed sensor is reliable and effective for DA determination in commercial samples. Moreover, the low values of RSD ranging from 1.7 % to 2.5 % show good precision of the proposed method.

3.8. Interference studies

The precise quantification of dopamine on the bare gold electrode is practically hampered in fluids containing some other biogenic molecules like for example ascorbic acid. As shown in Fig. 12a these two compounds oxidize on the unmodified Au electrode almost in the same potential range. Therefore, the subsequent objective of the study was to test the suitability of the developed Au/complex sensor for analytical study of DA in the mixture with AA. The corresponding voltammetric responses obtained with the Au/complex sensor are shown in Fig. 12b.

It can be observed that the deposition of Cu_4L_4 on the gold surface causes an increase of voltammetric signals of both analyzed substances and moreover significantly affects the peak-to-peak separation of considered processes. In the case of the Au/complex electrode, ΔE_p is 267 mV, while on the bare ΔE_p is equal to 56 mV. Thus, there is no doubt that the Au/complex electrode is suitable for simultaneous selective detection and analytical determination of dopamine in the presence of ascorbic acid and therefore also for determination of ascorbic acid in the presence of dopamine coexisting in a binary mixture.

In the binary mixture, the negative shift observed during dopamine oxidation and the positive shift recorded during AA oxidation on the Au/complex electrode can be attributed to electrostatic attraction and repulsion, which are caused by the presence of Cu_4L_4 complex, where the copper(II) ions are positively charged, the tridentate Schiff-base ligand is negative in charge, as is also the tetrafluoroborate anion. When referring to the representative schematic arrangement of the complex during electrochemical measurements (Fig. 5) the region that provides active sites for the oxidation of dopamine is exposed to the tetrafluoroborate anion, which would also explain the observed negative shifts. It is worth noting that similar behavior has been observed by Jiang et al., where acetate anions were the exposed negatively charged groups (while still coordinated to positively charged copper(II) ions) [16]. The effect of this process is to exclude most of the AA anions from the Cu_4L_4 modified electrode surface, causing a shift in the peak potential of the AA current toward a higher AA overpotential. At the same time, a reduction in the DA oxidation overpotential can be observed, the cause of which is the electrostatic attraction between Cu_4L_4 and positively charged DA cations.

The analytical sensitivity of the Au/complex sensor toward

Table 2

Determination of DA in a commercially available DA solution for infusion ($n = 3$).

Initial amount [mM]	Spiked amount [mM]	Found amount [mM]	Recovery [%] (Mean \pm SD)	RSD [%]
0.150	0	0.149	99.3 \pm 2.0	2.0
0.150	0.01	0.161	100.6 \pm 1.8	1.9
0.150	0.02	0.168	98.8 \pm 2.3	2.4
0.150	0.05	0.199	99.5 \pm 1.7	1.7
0.150	0.1	0.252	100.8 \pm 2.0	2.2
0.150	0.15	0.302	100.7 \pm 2.5	2.5

quantification of DA and AA in a binary mixture was determined by using the DPV technique and varying the concentration of one compound with that of the other kept constant. The DA concentration was changed in the range from 0.0001 mM to 1.5 mM and selected DPV voltammograms recorded in the presence of 0.5 mM of AA are shown in Fig. 13a. And conversely, the concentration of AA was varied from 0.5 mM to 5 mM, and selected DPV curves obtained in the presence of 0.5 mM DA are presented in Fig. 13b.

As expected, due to electrostatic interactions, the peaks corresponding to oxidation of the individual components of the tested binary mixture under investigation appear on the DPV at different potential values. An increase in the concentration of each component of the binary mixture results in an increase in the DPV signal corresponding to the oxidation of individual components of the tested mixture. Moreover, it should be noted that an increase in the concentration of each component in the studied mixture does not affect the peak potential at which DA and AA oxidize. This means that certainly the Au/complex electrode can be successfully applied for the analytical purposes intended in this work.

Fig. 14a and b shows the analysis of the peak currents versus concentration of individual compounds in the binary mixture under investigation.

By using the at least square method, the following linear regression equation was obtained for DA in the presence of constant amount of AA: $i_p \text{ [mA]} = 17 \cdot 10^{-2} c_{\text{DA}} \text{ [mM]} + 8 \cdot 10^{-2}$ ($R^2 = 0.9989$) in the LDR between 0.0001 mM and 0.75 mM. The LOD and LOQ values for DA quantification in this system were estimated as 5.4 nM and 18.0 nM, respectively. Note that LOD and LOQ values are analogous to those estimated for dopamine alone (see above). Meanwhile for AA in the presence of constant amount of DA in the LDR between 0.5 mM and 5 mM the rectilinear relationship is represented by the following linear regression equation: $i_p \text{ [mA]} = 19 \cdot 10^{-3} c_{\text{AA}} \text{ [mM]} + 17 \cdot 10^{-2}$ ($R^2 = 0.9986$), whereas the LOD and LOQ values are equal to 0.37 mM and 1.11 mM, respectively.

As above for DA alone, the practical application of the new Au/complex electrode for determination of DA in the presence of AA has been tested by the calibration method. For each studied sample, the measurements were repeated three times. The concentrations evaluated from calibration curves for both components of double mixture under investigation are very close to their nominal content in each sample, Table S2. On this basis, it is concluded that the presence of the interfering compound in the mixture with DA does not affect the quality of the quantitative analysis.

In addition to studying the effect of AA on DA quantitative determination, the effect of other possible interfering species on dopamine quantification at the Au/complex electrode has been investigated. For this purpose, various species (Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-}) at concentration of 5 mM were added to the supporting electrolyte solution (pH 7.0) containing 0.05 mM DA. It was observed that 100-fold excess of the aforementioned interferences had no effect on the DPV voltammetric signal derived from DA. The collected results are summarized in Table S3, and once again confirm that the designed modified Au/complex electrode shows good ability to specifically detect DA without any interference from the above species.

3.9. Electrode reproducibility and long-term stability of the modified electrode

To determine the reproducibility of the Au/complex electrode, five measurements were carried out in separate PBS solutions containing 0.05 mM dopamine. The calculated RSD values did not differ by more than 2.8 %, indicating the excellent reproducibility of the prepared new electrochemical sensor.

The long-term stability of the Au/complex electrode was examined every 8 days for 24 days in PBS solution containing 0.05 mM DA. Before and after each electrochemical measurement, the electrode was washed with water and dried in a stream of argon gas. For the time between

Fig. 12. (a) CVs recorded at the bare Au electrode in PBS (yellow) containing 0.5 mM DA (green) and 0.5 mM AA (blue), $dE/dt = 0.1 \text{ Vs}^{-1}$. (b) CVs recorded at Au/complex electrode in PBS (yellow) containing 0.5 mM DA (red), 0.5 mM AA (black), $dE/dt = 0.1 \text{ Vs}^{-1}$.

Fig. 13. DPVs recorded at the Au/complex electrode in PBS solution containing (a) 0.5 mM AA and increasing concentrations of DA (from 0.0001 mM to 0.5 mM) (b) 0.5 mM DA and increasing concentrations of AA (from 0.5 mM to 5 mM). $dE/dt = 0.1 \text{ Vs}^{-1}$.

Fig. 14. (a) The relationship between the peak current and concentration of DA in the presence of 0.5 mM AA (b) The relationship between the peak current and concentration of AA in the presence of 0.5 mM DA in a binary mixture. $dE/dt = 0.1 \text{ Vs}^{-1}$. Error bars correspond to the standard deviations of the measurements ($n = 3$).

measurements, the electrode was stored in an empty tube at room temperature. After 24 days, the voltammetric response decreased by about 4.9 % compared to the first measurement.

4. Conclusions

In summary, the tetrametallic copper(II) discrete $[4 \times 4]$ complex $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{L-H})_4(\text{BF}_4)_2(\text{MeOH})_2](\text{BF}_4)_2$ has been obtained and characterized. In addition, it was proven that the saddle-type complex promotes the formation of two regions, one having affinity for the gold electrode surface due to N-heterocycles and the other constituting a cavity with four copper ions as active centers for the catalytic oxidation of

dopamine. The prepared complex was used for modification of the gold electrode surface forming an excellent electrochemical sensor for dopamine sensing in aqueous medium, thus creating conditions similar to physiological ones. The measurements showed that the modified electrode has good selectivity, sensitivity, long-term stability and reproducibility. In addition, the Au/complex electrode is capable of detecting dopamine in the presence of interfering biogenic compounds such as ascorbic acid with low LOD and LOQ value of 5.4 nM and 18.0 nM, respectively. Additionally, other possible interfering species that may occur in the aqueous medium did not interfere with the dopamine detection. These results pave the way for further investigation of poly-metallic copper(II) complexes based on Schiff base ligands capable of

accumulation on the electrode surface and with an emphasis on their use as sensors for detecting neurotransmitters in the presence of interferents.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Daria Nowicka: Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Maciej Kubicki:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Violetta Patroniak:** Supervision, Resources, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Teresa Łuczak:** Investigation, Methodology, Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Data curation, Resources, Visualization, Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Adam Gorczyński:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available in the open data repository.

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Supplementary materials

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